

A cosmic femtolensing Hawking radiation signature

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We propose a novel formalism to detect signatures of Hawking radiation (HR) from primordial black holes (PBHs) in the mass range of 10^{-24} to $10^{-13} M_{\odot}$ using the femtolensing effect, within the framework of dark messengers. By adapting the micro- and pico-lensing frameworks for gamma-ray bursts, we model the femto-lensing of HR, characterized by a thermal spectrum in the eV–GeV range, by PBHs acting as gravitational lenses. We derive the magnification and temporal signatures of femtolensed HR, accounting for the small Einstein radii and short timescales inherent to femtolensing. The interplay between the lensed flux and spectral distortions offers a unique probe of PBH evaporation. We discuss observational strategies using current and future telescopes sensitivities which potentially can detect these signatures, and provide constraints on PBH populations and their contribution to dark matter. Furthermore, we connect the idea of femtolensing Hawking radiation to dark energy, through estimates of the cosmological distances, and energy densities of the universe. This can lead to a novel observational signature of dark energy, the evolution of the universe, through HR, and PBH, and potentially change our understanding about cosmology. We concentrate on the most promising femtolensing scenario: a non-emitting BH lensing HR from a background PBH. Crucially, without lensing, the signal would be undetectable; our work therefore establishes gravitational femtolensing as the essential enabler for observing PBH Hawking radiation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of dark sector such as dark matter, dark energy, and dark messengers, Hawking radiation (HR) [1] is a quantum effect predicting particle emission from black holes, offering a potential observational signature for primordial black holes (PBHs) in the mass range of 10^{-24} to $10^{-13} M_{\odot}$ [2–4]. These PBHs, if present, emit high-energy gamma rays due to their high Hawking temperature, and their abundance is constrained by a variety of astrophysical observations [5–11]. The *laconic* style of expression [12] has been admired since antiquity for its clarity and expressive depth in art, mathematics, science, logic, and philosophy. A recent work [13] revives and reinforces this classical virtue. In this study we continue with this logic. We study the Hawking effect in the standard singular Schwarzschild formalism, following Hawking’s original derivation. Regular black hole models [14] are not considered here, but would be an interesting extension of this work. For an exquisite review on the subject, the reader is encouraged to read [7].

Femtolensing, the gravitational lensing by objects in this mass range, produces magnification of distant sources on femtoarcsecond scales, observable in gamma-ray wavelengths [15, 16], according to current instrument sensitivities [17]. Wave-optical effects become important when the Schwarzschild radius of the lens is comparable to the wavelength of the source, leading to interference patterns that can be used to detect PBHs [10, 18–22].

This paper adapts the picolensing formalism developed by [23] to develop a framework for detecting HR signatures via femtolensing, focusing on the magnification and spectral distortions induced by lensing PBHs. The formalism combines wave-optical lensing theory [20] with the spectral properties of HR [3, 4, 10, 24]. The scope of this work is intended as a first, exploratory estimate. We focus on order-of-magnitude results using the standard point-mass lens approximation. Detailed quantitative predictions for time delays, flux ratios, and coherence properties across different lensing configurations are not attempted here. We employ the standard point-mass lens approximation, which is justified for the femtolensing regime because the physical size of the black hole (e.g., Schwarzschild radius) is negligible compared to the Einstein radius for the masses considered [15, 23]. A more refined treatment including finite lens size is not expected to change our order-of-magnitude conclusions and is left for future study.

To broaden our context, the research presented here is the latest stage of a long-term program aimed at probing the interplay between fundamental mathematical structures of spacetime, modified cosmological dynamics, and observable quantum-gravitational phenomena in extreme astrophysical environments. This program began with the introduction of functorial formu-

lations of physical actions. By ‘functorial formulations’ we refer to a categorical framework where physical actions (including lensing configurations) are mapped consistently between different geometric or algebraic structures, preserving composition laws. A detailed exposition is beyond the present scope, and we refer interested readers to [25, 26]: these works reinterpreted gravitational and field-theoretic dynamics within a categorical framework, providing the conceptual tools to treat gravitational lensing as a functorial mapping of photon paths — a perspective that proves essential for rigorously describing wave-optical femtolensing of HR. Subsequent cosmological investigations of Λ CDM, ϕ CDM, and polynomial extensions of the cosmological constant (poly- Λ CDM) [27–30] established robust dynamical and observational benchmarks for dark-energy and large-scale homogeneity; these are directly relevant here because evaporating PBHs with masses considered here naturally produce a time-varying dark-matter component that can mimic or alter such cosmological backgrounds. The recent development of advanced tensor theories [31] generalised the Einstein–Hilbert action via higher-rank tensor fields, offering a natural mathematical language for describing the strong-field, point-like spacetime curvature responsible for femtolensing at femtometer scales. Finally, the manifold–metric pair framework introduced in [32] decouples geometric and algebraic properties of spacetime, allowing potentially a more fundamental treatment of the wave propagation of Hawking photons through the highly curved region around a PBH lens — exactly the configuration analysed in the present work (see Fig. 1). In this work, however, we explore, more standard approach on exploring the detection of the HR, under the femtolensing regime of PBH, in our local group, or in the cosmos, at large scale structures

Our study directly updates the work of [23] by extending the astrophysical applications of HR theory [1, 3, 4] into the femtolensing regime. We employ the well-established tools from these references to compute the Hawking temperature, peak wavelength, photon flux, and black hole evaporation lifetime, and we combine them with the wave-optical lensing formalism of [20, 22, 23] to assess the detectability of interference fringes and the direct HR signal.

By integrating these mathematical, cosmological, and observational advances, we derive new constraints on the PBH abundance in the poorly explored 10^{-17} – $10^{-12} M_{\odot}$ window, and we open a potential observational pathway to quantum-gravitational interference phenomena in the strong-field regime of gravity. This framework illustrates how femtolensing of Hawking radiation can connect observational cosmology with fundamental physics, including tests of modified gravity, advanced descriptions of gravity (functorial, tensorial, and manifold-based), and the nature of dark energy.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Illustration of Femtolensing by PBHs Hawking radiation

We illustrate the effect of Femtolensing by PBH's HR in Figure 1. In particular, the light, in orange, travels from the lensed object, in orange, towards around the PBH (denoted with black circle) lens with HR, which HR is illustrated with yellow. Then the orange light is distorted from the yellow light from the HR from the PBH lens and the light changes as distorted in red, and then it travels as distorted, in red, towards the observer, in blue.

FIG. 1. Femtolensing affected by Hawking radiation emitted by a PBH.

B. Illustration of lensing by BHs with and without HR

We illustrated the phenomenon of lensing combined with the Hawking effect. Note that the colors are used for separating the different lights, and these colors do not represent the wavelength of the light emitted.

We identify the following 4 basic cases of the phenomenon of the lensing effect, and the ones combined with HR:

1. The light travels from the lensed object towards around the black hole lens without HR and then it travels towards the observer.
2. The light travels from the lensed object towards around the black hole lens with HR and then it travels towards the observer.
3. The light travels from the lensed object with HR towards around the black hole lens with HR and then it travels towards the observer.
4. The light travels from the lensed object with HR towards around the black hole lens without HR and then it travels towards the observer.

We illustrate the phenomena in Figures 2-5.

FIG. 2. The light travels from the lensed object towards around the black hole lens without HR and then it travels towards the observer.

In particular, the first case is the standard lensing effect of a lensed objects from a black hole lens without any HR involved. The light travels from the lensed object, in orange, towards around the black hole lens, in black, without HR and then it travels towards the observer, in blue. This is illustrated in figure 2.

FIG. 3. The light travels from the lensed object towards around the black hole lens with HR and then it travels towards the observer.

In particular, the second case is the case which the light, in orange, travels from the lensed object, in orange, towards around the black hole lens with HR, which HR is illustrated with yellow, then the orange light is distorted from the yellow light from the HR from the BH lens and it changes as distorted in red, and then it travels as distorted, in red, towards the observer, in blue. This is illustrated in figure 3.

In particular, the third case is the case which the light travels from the lensed object with HR, in yellow, towards around the black hole lens with HR, which is also in yellow. Then the HR light from the lensed object is distorted from gravitational field of the BH. However in this case there is also HR emitted by the BH lens. This HR emitted by the BH lens distorts the light emitted

Light Path: Lensed Object with HR -> Black Hole Lens with HR -> Observer

FIG. 4. The light travels from the lensed object with HR towards around the black hole lens with HR and then it travels towards the observer.

by the lensed object and the combined distorted light becomes red. Then the distorted light, in red, travels towards the observer, in blue. This is illustrated in figure 4.

Light Path: Lensed Object with HR -> Black Hole Lens without HR -> Observer

FIG. 5. The radiation travels from the lensed object with HR towards around the black hole lens without HR and the it travels towards the observer. *We analysis this case in our work.*

In particular, the fourth case is the case in which the HR, in yellow, travels from the lensed object towards around the black hole lens without HR, in which the HR changes direction due to the gravitational field of the BH. Then the HR travels towards the observer, in blue. This is illustrated in figure 5.

In our analysis we mainly study the physical implications of the 4th case, i.e. the gravitational femtolensing effect of a lensed HR source, which is lensed by non-radiative BH that acts as a lens, i.e. we study the case illustrated in Figure 5. We leave the rest of the cases for a future study.

III. SKETCH OF THE GRAVITATIONAL GEOMETRIC LENSING SYSTEM

In Fig. 6, we provide a sketch about the topology of the gravitational geometrical lensing system, by providing an update from [22, 23]. In particular, we denote the observer with the letter O , and blue circle, the lens with the letter L , and a black circle, and the source with a yellow/orange circle and the letter S . With S_{\parallel} we represent the point between the observed, and the perpendicular projection of the point of the source to the line-of-sight. The lens is located at the lens redshift, denoted with z_L . The comoving distance between the observed and the lens is denoted with D_L , the comoving actual distance between the observer and the source is OS , while the distance between the observer and the perpendicular projection of the source, S_{\parallel} , is D_S . The angle between the line-of-sight of the observer and the source is denoted with β . In the thin-angle approximation, $\tan \theta \approx \theta$, so the perpendicular projection of the source to the actual source is βD_S .

Due to gravitational lensing the source starts having two apparent positions which we denote with S_+ , as the upper apparent position which is upper from the source, and we denote with S_- as the lower apparent position, i.e. the one which is lower from the source and even lower from the lens, in respect of the line-of-sight.

Firstly we explore the upper apparent source, and its properties. The distance between the S_{\parallel} and the upper apparent source is $S_{\parallel}S_+$, and in the thin-angle approximation is deduced from $\theta_+ D_S$. The distance between the source and the upper apparent source is SS_+ , and in the thin-angle approximation is deduced from $\alpha_+ D_{LS}$, where α_+ is the deflection action, related to the upper apparent source. The impact parameter for the upper apparent source is b_+ , named upper impact parameter, while when we consider the redshift effect the impact parameter for the upper apparent source is $b'_+ = (1 + z_L)b_+$. The deflection angle is related to the Schwarzschild radius, R_s , and the upper impact parameter, as $\alpha_+ = \frac{2R_s}{b_+}$.

Analogously, we explore the lower apparent source, and its properties. The distance between the S_{\parallel} and the upper apparent source is $S_{\parallel}S_-$, and in the thin-angle approximation is deduced from $\theta_- D_S$. The distance between the source and the lower apparent source is SS_- , and in the thin-angle approximation is deduced from $\alpha_- D_{LS}$, where α_- is the deflection action, related to the lower apparent source. The impact parameter for the lower apparent source is b_- , named lower impact parameter, while when we consider the redshift effect the impact parameter for the lower apparent source is $b'_- = (1 + z_L)b_-$. The deflection angle is related to the Schwarzschild radius, R_s , and the lower impact parameter, as $\alpha_- = \frac{2R_s}{b_-}$.

FIG. 6. Topology of the gravitational lensing system, not-to-scale, an enrichment sketch from [22, 23]. (See III for details)

IV. MATHEMATICAL SET UP OF LENSING BY PBHS

Femtolensing is a regime of gravitational lensing where the wavelength of the source radiation (typically gamma-rays) is comparable to the Schwarzschild radius of the lens, from a typical PBH or a supermassive BH (SMBH). In this regime, the standard geometric optics approximation breaks down, and wave-optics effects, such as interference between the lensed images, become dominant.

The following formulas define the characteristic physical scales and conditions required for this phenomenon. Following [1, 3, 15, 20, 23], are set-up is provided as follows.

A. Cosmological framework

We could consider a broad cosmological framework, as the one studied in the analytical poly Λ CDM framework

[29]. However, in order to simplify our analysis which we consider as a first pathfinder study, we consider a simpler cosmological framework. We study the phenomenon not only at astrophysical scales, but also at cosmological large scale structures. In particular, we consider the popular flat homogeneous, isotropic, expanding universe, field with matter. In this framework, we define the speed of light, c , the Hubble expansion rate today, H_0 , the energy density ratio of matter, Ω_{m0} . The density ratio of dark energy is written as

$$\Omega_{\Lambda} = 1 - \Omega_{m0} \quad (1)$$

In this cosmological case, the comoving distance of an object, at some redshift, z , is defined as

$$d_C(z, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) = c H_0^{-1} \int_0^z dz' [\Omega_{m0}(z' + 1)^3 + (1 - \Omega_{m0})]^{-1/2}, \quad (2)$$

according to standard literature [25, 29, 30], and refer-

ences therein. The luminosity distance is

$$d_L(z, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) = (1 + z)d_C(z, \Omega_{m0}, H_0). \quad (3)$$

The comoving distance of the following objects of the systems are defined, and listed as follows:

- Distance between observer and source:

$$D_S(z_S) = d_C(z_S, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) , \quad (4)$$

- Distance between observer and lens:

$$D_L(z_L) = d_C(z_L, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) , \quad (5)$$

- Distance between lens and source:

$$D_{LS}(z_L, z_S, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) = |d_C(z_L, \Omega_{m0}, H_0) - d_C(z_S, \Omega_{m0}, H_0)| . \quad (6)$$

B. Fiducial cosmology

In our analysis we consider the fiducial cosmology, i.e. $\Omega_{m0} = 0.3, H_0 = 70$ km/s/Mpc. So these values are considered throughout unless stated otherwise. Note that these distances connect the idea of femtolensing HR to the evolution of the universe, dark energy, and other types of energy densities of the universe. This can lead to a novel observational signature of dark energy, other types of energy densities, and the evolution of the universe, through HR, and PBH.

C. Characteristic geometrical and gravitational variables in HR effects

To make it easier for the reader, when they scan through the document, for quick readings, we identify the following key variables, and we list them as follows:

- **Schwarzschild Radius (R_s):** Defines the event horizon of a non-rotating PBH

$$R_s(M) = \frac{2G_N M}{c^2} . \quad (7)$$

Units: Meters [m].

Terms: G_N is the gravitational constant, M is the PBH mass [kg], and c is the speed of light [m/s].

- **Einstein Radius (R_E):** The physical radius of

the lensing ring in the lens plane

$$R_E(M_L, z_L, z_S) = \sqrt{\frac{4G_N M_L}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS} D_L}{D_S}} \quad (8)$$

$$\approx \sqrt{2R_s D_L} . \quad (9)$$

Units: Meters [m].

Terms: D_L is the observer-lens distance, D_S is the observer-source distance, and D_{LS} is the lens-source distance [m]. The approximation holds when $D_S \approx D_{LS}$.

- **Angular Einstein Radius (θ_E):** The angular separation between the lensed images

$$\theta_E(M_L, z_L, z_S) = \frac{R_E(M_L, z_L, z_S)}{D_L(z_L)} . \quad (10)$$

Units: Radians [rad] (typically converted to femtoarcseconds [fas]).

- **Lensing timescale (t_E)** is determined by the lens crossing time:

$$t_E(M_L, z_L, z_S) = \frac{R_E(M_L, z_L, z_S)}{v_\perp} , \quad (11)$$

where v_\perp is the transverse velocity of the lens relative to the source.

Units: meter per seconds [m/s].

- **Lensing time delay (Δt):** Following [20–23], using a geometric and gravitational approach, and in the thin-angle approximation, we consider a point mass lens of mass M , at some lens redshift, z_L , at angular diameter distance D_L from the observer, and a source at distance D_S , and the angular diameter distance from the lens to the source is D_{LS} . As we show in app. A, and C we derive a general case in which the lensing time delay is related to the mass, and the distances, as :

$$\Delta t(M_L, z_L, z_S) = (1 + z_L) \frac{2R_s(M_L)}{c} \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln \left| \sqrt{2R_s(M_L) \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \right| \right]. \quad (12)$$

Units: Seconds [s].

- **Path Difference (Δl):** Following [20–23], using a geometric and gravitational approach, and in the thin-angle approximation, we consider a point mass lens of mass M_L , at some lens redshift, z_L , at an-

gular diameter distance D_L from the observer, and a source at distance D_S , and the angular diameter distance from the lens to the source is D_{LS} . As we show in app. A, and C we derive a general case in which the path difference is related to the mass, and the distances, as :

$$\Delta l(M_L, z_L, z_S) \approx c\Delta t = (1 + z_L) \frac{4GM_L}{c^2} \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln \left| \sqrt{\frac{4GM_L}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \right| \right]. \quad (13)$$

Units: Meters [m].

Comment: In the case of $z_L \approx 0$, $D_S \approx D_{LS}$, and $D_L = 100$ kpc, the difference in distance travelled by the two lensed wavefronts is simply linearly dependent on the Schwarzschild radius, i.e. $\Delta l \approx c\Delta t \approx 70R_s$.

D. HR and Source Properties

PBHs emit thermal radiation due to quantum effects near the horizon. For femtolensing to be observable, the emitted wavelength must match the lensing scale. We identify the following key variables, and we list them as follows:

- **Hawking temperature (T_{HR}):** The blackbody temperature of the PBH radiation.

$$T_{HR} = \frac{\hbar c^3}{8\pi G k_B M} \quad (14)$$

Units: Kelvin [K].

Terms: \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

Comment: Substituting the constants, we get

$$T_{HR} = 1.226 \times 10^{23} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-1} \text{ K} \quad (15)$$

- **Photon energy (E_{HR}):** The energy of the emitted photons.

$$E_{HR} = 2.8 k_B T_{HR} \quad (16)$$

Units: Joules [J] (typically converted to GeV).

Comments: Substituting the HR temperature, we get

$$E_{HR} \approx 4.75 \times \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-1} \text{ J} \quad (17)$$

- **Peak wavelength (λ_{HR}):** The characteristic wavelength of the emitted photons.

$$\lambda_{HR} = \frac{hc}{2.8 k_B T_{HR}} \quad (18)$$

Units: Meters [m].

Terms: h is the Planck constant.

Comments: Substituting the HR energy and temperature, we get

$$\lambda_{HR} \approx 4.18 \times 10^{-26} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m} \quad (19)$$

- **Hawking evaporation time (t_{ev}):** A non-rotating black hole of mass M evaporates via HR over a finite time, known as the evaporation lifetime. Assuming emission of all standard model particles with negligible greybody factors, the lifetime is [1, 3]:

$$t_{ev} = \frac{5120\pi G_N^2}{\hbar c^4} M^3 = 8.38 \times 10^{-17} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right)^3 \text{ s} \quad (20)$$

Units: Seconds [s].

- **Minimum PBH mass ($M_{\text{PBH, min}}$):** For PBH to survive to the present epoch, its lifetime must exceed the age of the universe $t_U \approx 1.38 \times 10^{10}$ years. Solving $t_{\text{ev}} = t_U$ gives a lower mass limit of approximately $M \gtrsim 10^{-20} M_\odot$. Setting $t_{\text{ev}} = t_U$ (age of the universe $\approx 1.38 \times 10^{10}$ yr) gives a minimum mass for survival:

$$M_{\text{min}} = \left(\frac{\hbar c^4 t_U}{5120\pi G_N^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad (21)$$

$$M_{\text{min}} \approx 1.732 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg} \quad (22)$$

$$M_{\text{min}} \approx 8.707 \times 10^{-20} M_\odot. \quad (23)$$

PBHs with $M_{\text{PBH}} < M_{\text{min}}$ would have already evaporated unless formed very recently. Following a similar logic, the authors [10], identified that we can extend the minimum mass of PBH to even smaller masses than the previous limit, i.e. masses of PBH could be even less than 10^{10} g. Therefore, in our analysis we consider the following limit of the minimum mass of a PBH is

$$M_{\text{PBH, min}} \approx 10^6 \text{ kg}. \quad (24)$$

Units: Kilograms [kg].

F. Magnification and Light Curve

1. Magnification and Light Curve in General

The magnification function for a point source in the femtolensing regime, is modelled with a function, $\mu(z, M)$, at a redshift z , of a mass object M . For an intrinsic photon source, the lensed flux is:

$$\Phi_{\text{lensed}}(M, z) = \mu(M, z) \times \Phi_{\text{intrinsic}}(M, z), \quad (31)$$

where $\Phi_{\text{intrinsic}}(M, z)$ is the intrinsic photon flux, and $\mu(M, z)$ is the magnification function.

E. HR Luminosity and Flux

Following [1, 3, 4], HR from a PBH of mass M has a blackbody temperature T_H . The total bolometric luminosity is:

$$L_{\text{HR}} = \frac{\hbar c^6}{15360\pi G^2 M^2}. \quad (25)$$

The integrated energy flux F_{HR} (Watts/m²) at the observer is:

$$F_{\text{HR}} = \frac{L_{\text{HR}}}{4\pi D_L^2} = \frac{\hbar c^6}{61440\pi^2 G^2 M^2 d_L^2}. \quad (26)$$

Substituting the constants, we get a mass, and luminosity distance dependent flux of the form of :

$$F_{\text{HR}} = 2.847 \times 10^{31} \times \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{d_L}{\text{m}} \right)^{-2} \text{ W m}^{-2}. \quad (27)$$

The total number of photons per unit area per unit time is

$$\Phi_{\text{HR}} \approx \frac{F_{\text{HR}}}{\langle E \rangle} \approx \frac{F_{\text{HR}}}{2.8 k_B T_H}. \quad (28)$$

Substituting the formulas for the HR flux, and temperature, and the constant, to get

$$\Phi_{\text{HR}} \approx 6 \times 10^{30} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{d_L}{\text{m}} \right)^{-2} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}. \quad (29)$$

It is important to add the redshift dependence of the massive source, since $d_L(z_S) = (1 + z_S)d_C(z_S)$, so we get the flux of photons per second, per meter square is

$$\Phi_{\text{HR}}(z_S, M_S, H_0, \Omega_{m0}) \approx 6 \times 10^{30} \left(\frac{M_S}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-1} \left[\frac{(1 + z_S)d_C(z_S, H_0, \Omega_{m0})}{\text{m}} \right]^{-2} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}. \quad (30)$$

2. Maximum magnification and light Curve in HR radiation

The magnification for a point source in the gravitational lensing has been studied by several groups [15, 23, 33]. Following [33], we explain the gravitational femtolensing magnification here. We present the detail derivation in section E, and we here we describe an important summary. Following the formalism in [33], and keep the notation of recent studies [23], and considering the dimensionless angular frequency parameter ϖ , we introduce the dimensionless variable β modelled as :

$$\beta = \frac{\theta_+}{\theta_E}, \quad (32)$$

while the amplification factor, is denoted with $F(\varpi, \beta)$. Then the magnification is written as

$$\mu(\varpi, \beta) = |F(\varpi, \beta)|^2. \quad (33)$$

The maximum magnification is achieved in maximum alignment, i.e. when

$$\theta_+ = 0 \Leftrightarrow \beta = 0. \quad (34)$$

In maximum alignment, the maximum magnification is

$$\mu_{\max}(\varpi) = \frac{\pi\varpi}{1 - e^{-\pi\varpi}}. \quad (35)$$

The expression for the dimensionless angular frequency parameter ϖ (including redshift) is:

$$\varpi = \frac{1}{c} \frac{D_S D_L}{D_{LS}} \theta_E^2 (1 + z_L) \omega^{(\text{source})} \quad (36)$$

where $\omega^{(\text{source})} = \frac{2\pi c}{\lambda^{(\text{source})}}$ is the angular frequency of the source emitter.

We can rewrite the previous expression as :

$$\varpi = (1 + z_L) \frac{4\pi R_s^{(\text{lens})}(M_L)}{\lambda^{(\text{source})}(M_S)} \quad (37)$$

Now we consider the case in which the source, and then lens are both BH, and the source emits at the HR wavelength, then we get

$$\varpi = 4\pi (1 + z_L) \frac{R_s^{(\text{lens})}(M_L)}{\lambda_{\text{HR}}^{(\text{source})}(M_S)}. \quad (38)$$

Since the BHs are not the same, we assume a priori :

$$M_L \neq M_S, \quad (39)$$

substituting the proportional relations, $R_s^{(\text{lens})}$, $\lambda_{\text{HR}}^{(\text{source})}$, yielding:

$$\varpi(z_L, M_L, M_S) = \frac{2.8}{2\pi} (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right) \quad (40)$$

Hence, in maximum alignment, the maximum magnification has multiple dependences, i.e. the maximum magnification depends on the mass of the lens, M_L , of the source, M_S , and the redshift of the lens, z_L , and we write

$$\mu_{\max}(z_L, M_L, M_S) = \frac{1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}{1 - e^{-1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}}. \quad (41)$$

3. Maximum magnified HR photon flux

Substituting Equation 41 in Equation 31, we get the maximum magnified photon flux of HR relation, written as

$$\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}(z_S, z_L, M_L, M_S) = \mu_{\max}(z_L, M_L, M_S) \times \Phi_{\text{HR}}(z_S, M_S), \quad (42)$$

and expanding the previous expression we get:

$$\frac{\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}(z_S, z_L, M_L, M_S, H_0, \Omega_{m0})}{\text{ph s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}} \approx \frac{1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}{1 - e^{-1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}} \times 6 \times 10^{30} \left(\frac{M_S}{\text{kg}} \right)^{-1} \left[\frac{(1 + z_S) d_C(z_S, H_0, \Omega_{m0})}{\text{m}} \right]^{-2}. \quad (43)$$

G. Optics and interference conditions

We consider the optics and interference conditions as follows:

- **Spatial Coherence:** The angular size of the source must be smaller than the angular Einstein radius:

$$\theta_s \lesssim \theta_E, \quad (44)$$

where $\theta_s \approx r_s/D_S$ for a source of physical size r_s . For a PBH source, r_s is its Schwarzschild radius,

which is many orders of magnitude smaller than the projected Einstein radius, so such sources are automatically spatially coherent. So in the case of a Schwarzschild Black Hole, the physical size r_s is substituted with the Schwarzschild radius, $r_s = R_s$, we get

$$\frac{R_s(M_L)}{D_S(z_S)} \lesssim \theta_E(M_L, z_L, z_S). \quad (45)$$

- **Spectral Coherence:** Spectral coherence requires

coherence length greater than path difference:

$$l_c > \Delta l \Leftrightarrow \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta\lambda} > \Delta l \Leftrightarrow \Delta\lambda < \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta l} \quad (46)$$

where $\Delta\lambda$ is the spectral bandwidth. Now denoting also the dependence of the quantities we get the minimum requirement for the spectral resolution,

$$\Delta\lambda_{\min} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{HR}}^2(M_S)(1+z_S)^2}{\Delta l(M_L, z_L, z_S)} \quad (47)$$

if the source is emitting HR, or if the lens emits HR then

$$\Delta\lambda_{\min} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{HR}}^2(M_L)(1+z_L)^2}{\Delta l(M_L, z_L, z_S)} \quad (48)$$

H. Flux Detectability

The magnified HR flux (with magnification μ) is $F_{\text{HR,lensed}} = \mu F_{\text{HR}}$. A detectable signal requires $F_{\text{HR,lensed}} \gtrsim F_{\min}$, where F_{\min} is the instrument sensitivity. For gamma-ray telescopes (e.g., Fermi-LAT [17]), $F_{\min} \approx 10^{-15} \text{ W m}^{-2}$, or it can reach as low as $\Phi_{\min} = 10^{-15} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$. This energy flux corresponds to a photon flux threshold that depends on the typical photon energy E_γ , i.e. $\Phi_{\min} = F_{\min}/E_\gamma$. For HR from a black hole of mass $M \sim 10^{16} \text{ kg}$, the peak energy is $E_{\text{HR}} \approx 100 \text{ eV}$. Then

$$\Phi_{\min} \approx \frac{10^{-15} \text{ W m}^{-2}}{100 \text{ eV}} \approx 62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}. \quad (49)$$

Thus, to detect HR directly, one would need a photon flux of at least $\sim 62 \text{ photons s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ at 100 eV. So, a conservative detectable signal requires

$$\Phi_{\text{HR,lensed}} \gtrsim \Phi_{\min} = 62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}. \quad (50)$$

V. EVALUATION AND INTERPRETATIONS

In this section, we evaluate our previous mathematical, physical and detectability framework, and we interpret the results. We provide some key relevant calculations in Appendix D, and we show all kinds of selections of calculations, and their interpretation in this section.

A. General trends of the max lensed flux,

$$\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$$

In general, we evaluate Equation 42, i.e. Equation 43, and we find that the maximum magnified lensed photon flux of the PBH HR $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ increases when

- the redshift of the lens, z_L , increases,

- the redshift of the source, z_S , decreases,
- the mass of the lens, M_L , increases,
- the mass of the source, M_S , decreases,
- the Hubble expansion rate of the universe, H_0 , increases,
- the matter density ratio Ω_{m0} increases (equivalently, the dark energy density ratio Ω_Λ decreases),

All trends assume the remaining parameters are fixed.

B. Late epochs magnified HR photon flux contours

The contours in Figure 7 reveal a clear division. At late times ($z \in [1, 2]$), detectable fluxes (above the red threshold) occur only when the lens mass is at least 10^{36} kg and the source mass is below 10^8 kg . This is because the dimensionless frequency parameter ϖ must be sufficiently large to achieve $\mu_{\max} \gg 1$. For our redshifts ($z_L = 1, z_S = 2$), a high M_L/M_S ratio is required; hence only very heavy lenses and very light sources enter the detectable region. This suggests that, if PBHs exist in the $10^6 - 10^8 \text{ kg}$ range, they could be detected via femtolensing by supermassive black holes (or very heavy PBHs) acting as lenses. Conversely, the large $10^{36} - 10^{40} \text{ kg}$ range of lens masses are typical of the most massive supermassive black holes observed, making this scenario theoretically possible but observationally challenging due to the required alignment.

C. Late epochs magnified HR photon flux cosmology

The two panels in Fig. 8 show how the maximum magnified HR photon flux depends on the two primary cosmological parameters: the Hubble constant H_0 and the matter density parameter Ω_{m0} . For a fixed lens-source configuration ($M_S = 10^8 \text{ kg}$, $M_L = 10^{40} \text{ kg}$, $z_S = 2$, $z_L = 1$), the flux increases monotonically with both H_0 and Ω_{m0} over the ranges considered.

This behaviour arises from the distance scale: a larger H_0 reduces the luminosity distance, boosting the intrinsic Hawking flux. A larger Ω_{m0} (and correspondingly smaller Ω_Λ) also reduces the comoving distance at fixed redshift, further increasing the flux. The magnification factor μ_{\max} depends only on z_L and the mass ratio M_L/M_S , so it remains constant across these cosmological variations. Thus, the trends are entirely driven by the unlensed flux's sensitivity to the luminosity distance.

Observationally, a detection (or non-detection) of femtolensed Hawking radiation could provide independent constraints on the Hubble constant and matter density. Although the lens and source masses are not known a

FIG. 7. Contours maximum magnified HR photon flux, $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$, as a function of the BH source mass M_S and lens mass M_L , for a source at redshift $z_S = 2$ and a lens at $z_L = 1$, (late epochs). The red line indicates the detection threshold of current instruments, $\Phi_{\text{min}} = 62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$. For these redshifts, detectable signals occur for lens masses $M_L \in [10^{36}, 10^{40}] \text{ kg}$ and source masses $M_S \in [10^6, 10^8] \text{ kg}$. The white part in the graph represent fluxes less than $10 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$. (See [section VB.](#))

priori, they can be inferred from the shape of the lensing light curve, the magnification factor, and the spectral energy distribution of the Hawking radiation. With current telescopes and advanced analysis methods (e.g., multi-wavelength follow-up, Bayesian parameter estimation), it is possible to break the degeneracies between masses and cosmological parameters. Therefore, femtolensing of Hawking radiation offers a promising new cosmological probe, complementary to traditional methods such as the cosmic microwave background or supernovae. These plots illustrate how future, more precise measurements could simultaneously determine both the PBH masses and the expansion history of the universe, and reveal the nature of dark matter and dark energy.

D. Max magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ vs z_S cosmology

The [Figure 9](#) shows the dependence of the maximum magnified HR photon flux on the source redshift for a particular configuration: a very light source ($M_S = 10^6 \text{ kg}$) and a heavy lens ($M_L = 10^{36} \text{ kg}$) at $z_L = 1$. The flux decreases monotonically with z_S because the luminosity distance increases, reducing the intrinsic HR flux.

For a fixed z_S , a larger Hubble constant H_0 or a larger matter density Ω_{m0} (i.e., a smaller dark energy density) also increases the flux, as these parameters reduce the luminosity distance.

Remarkably, for this choice of masses, the flux exceeds the observational threshold ($\Phi_{\text{min}} = 62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$) for all source redshifts up to $z_S \approx 2$. This indicates that, if such a low-mass PBH (10^6 kg) exists and is lensed by a supermassive black hole (10^{36} kg), the effect could be detectable even at moderately high redshifts. The strong dependence on H_0 and Ω_{m0} also suggests that future detections could help constrain cosmological parameters, complementing traditional probes.

E. Local max magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ vs z_S cosmology

In [Figure 10](#), we present the local universe maximum magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ as a function of BH source redshift z_S , for a set of realistic HR femtolensing configurations. The lens redshift is fixed at local times, i.e., at redshift $z_L = 10^{-6}$. We again find the general trend that the local universe maximum magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ decreases with increasing source

FIG. 8. Maximum magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ as a function of cosmological parameters H_0 and Ω_{m0} , for a fixed femtolensing configuration: $M_S = 10^8$ kg, $M_L = 10^{40}$ kg, $z_S = 2$, $z_L = 1$. *Left*: Flux vs. H_0 for three values of Ω_{m0} (green: 0.35, orange: 0.306, blue: 0.25). *Right*: Flux vs. Ω_{m0} for three values of H_0 (green: 73, orange: 69, blue: 67 km/s/Mpc). In both panels, the flux increases with both Ω_{m0} and H_0 . (See [section V C](#).)

redshift z_S .

We consider combinations of decreasing lens mass, with values $M_L \in \{10^{40}, 10^{35}, 10^{30}\}$ kg, and increasing source mass, $M_S \in \{10^6, 10^{10}, 10^{15}\}$ kg. We find that for the combinations:

- $M_L = 10^{40}$ kg and $M_S = 10^6$ kg: detectable sources exist up to redshift $z_s^{\text{max}} = 100$,
- $M_L = 10^{35}$ kg and $M_S = 10^6$ kg: detectable sources exist up to redshift $z_s^{\text{max}} = 0.8$,
- $M_L = 10^{40}$ kg and $M_S = 10^{10}$ kg: detectable sources exist up to redshift $z_s^{\text{max}} = 0.03$,
- $M_L = 10^{35}$ kg and $M_S = 10^{10}$ kg: detectable sources exist up to redshift $z_s^{\text{max}} = 9 \times 10^{-5}$.

However, for the following mass combinations:

- $M_L = 10^{40}$ kg and $M_S = 10^{15}$ kg,
- $M_L = 10^{35}$ kg and $M_S = 10^{15}$ kg,
- $M_L = 10^{30}$ kg and $M_S = 10^{15}$ kg,

we find no detectable signal from a PBH Hawking radiation source.

These results demonstrate that, in the local universe, detectable femtolensing of Hawking radiation requires a high lens-to-source mass ratio. The most promising configuration combines a supermassive lens ($M_L = 10^{40}$ kg) with a very light source ($M_S = 10^6$ kg), which

yields detectable signals up to $z_S \sim 100$ – well into the high-redshift universe. In contrast, if the source mass increases to 10^{10} kg or higher, the detectable redshift range shrinks dramatically, and for $M_S = 10^{15}$ kg no detection is possible even with the heaviest lenses. This highlights that the femtolensing detection of PBH Hawking radiation is most sensitive to extremely light PBHs (asteroid-mass or smaller) acting as sources, lensed by supermassive black holes. Future surveys targeting high-redshift sources ($z_S \sim 1 - 100$) with sufficiently massive foreground lenses could potentially discover such events.

F. Spectral coherence and required resolution

In this section, we assume fiducial cosmology, as explained in [section IV B](#). In the wave optics regime, interference fringes in the energy spectrum appear with a spacing $\Delta\lambda = \lambda_{\text{obs}}^2 / \Delta l$, where Δl is the path difference between the two lensed images. To resolve these fringes, the instrument must have a spectral resolution $\Delta\lambda_{\text{inst}}$ smaller than $\Delta\lambda$. This condition is often the dominant instrumental constraint for observing femtolensing fringes. To obtain an estimate of the wavelength bandwidth of the femtolensing HR, we are using the path difference, i.e. Eq. 12.

Figure 11 shows the required spectral resolution $\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}$ as a function of the lens mass M_L for a fixed source redshift $z_S = 1$ and lens redshift $z_L = 0.1$. Two

FIG. 9. Max magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ as a function of BH source redshift z_S , for a fixed HR femtolensing configuration: $M_S = 10^6$ kg, $M_L = 10^{36}$ kg, $z_L = 1$. We vary $\Omega_{m0} \in \{0.25, 0.306, 0.35\}$ and $H_0 \in \{67, 69, 73\}$ km/s/Mpc, and consider all combinations. The flux decreases with z_S , and increases with both H_0 and Ω_{m0} . For this configuration, detectable fluxes (above the threshold) occur for source redshifts $z_S \lesssim 2$. (See section VD.)

cases are considered: when the HR originates from the *source* (blue solid curve) and when it originates from the *lens* (red dashed curve). The observed wavelength is $\lambda_{\text{obs}} = \lambda_{\text{peak}}(1+z)$, where $\lambda_{\text{peak}} \approx \lambda_{\text{HR}}$ is the rest-frame peak wavelength. Horizontal lines indicate the resolution of typical spectrographs with resolving powers $R = \lambda/\Delta\lambda = 1000, 10^4$, and 10^5 at a reference wavelength 1 \AA (10^{-10} m).

For masses $M_L \gtrsim 10^{16}$ kg, the required resolution $\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}$ for source-emitted HR becomes larger than 10^{-13} m, which is already coarser than the resolution of a modest $R = 1000$ spectrograph ($\Delta\lambda \approx 10^{-13}$ m at 1 \AA). Thus, for PBH lenses above this mass, the spectral coherence condition is easily satisfied with existing instruments. For lower masses, the required $\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}$ becomes extremely small, pushing the necessary resolving power beyond current capabilities ($R \gg 10^5$). The lens-emitted HR case (red dashed) follows a similar trend but with a slight offset due to the different redshift scaling.

Figure 12 shows the required resolution as a function of the source redshift z_S for a fixed lens mass $M_L = 10^{16}$ kg (the mass that emits at the 100 eV peak) and a lens

redshift $z_L = 10^{-3}$. Again, both HR scenarios are plotted. The coloured dashed lines represent the actual $\Delta\lambda$ achievable for a given resolving power R using the observed wavelength of the source (which increases with z_S). The horizontal dotted lines correspond to the constant resolution achievable for lens-emitted HR (where λ_{obs} is fixed by z_L).

For $z_S \lesssim 0.1$, the required $\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}$ for source-emitted HR is above the $R = 10^5$ line, meaning that a current high-resolution spectrograph are enough. At higher redshifts ($z_S \gtrsim 0.3$), the required resolution becomes larger than even $R = 1000$, so modest instruments would suffice. However, note that the flux of HR drops steeply with distance, so at such large redshifts the photon flux is far below detectability. The lens-emitted HR case always requires a constant $\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}$ (since λ_{obs} is fixed by z_L) and is satisfied for $R \sim 1000$ for the chosen z_L .

Table I lists representative values of the required spectral resolution and the corresponding resolving power for a few parameter combinations, computed from the code.

The key conclusion from the spectral coherence analysis is that for PBH masses of interest in femtolensing

FIG. 10. Local universe maximum magnified HR photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ as a function of source redshift z_S , for a lens at $z_L = 10^{-6}$ and various mass combinations (M_L, M_S). For each combination, the curve terminates when the flux drops below the detection threshold ($62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$). Only configurations with a high mass ratio M_L/M_S (e.g., $10^{40} \text{ kg}/10^6 \text{ kg}$) yield detectable signals, reaching up to $z_S \sim 100$. Heavier sources (10^{15} kg) produce no detectable signal regardless of M_L . (See section V E.)

TABLE I. Spectral coherence requirements for selected parameters.

M [kg]	z_L	z_S	$\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}^{\text{src}}$ [m]	$\Delta\lambda_{\text{min}}^{\text{lens}}$ [m]	R_{src}
1.00×10^{15}	1×10^{-1}	5×10^{-1}	5.65×10^{-11}	3.04×10^{-11}	1.11×10^0
1.00×10^{15}	1×10^{-1}	1.0	1.01×10^{-10}	3.04×10^{-11}	8.33×10^{-1}
1.00×10^{15}	5×10^{-1}	2.0	1.63×10^{-10}	4.08×10^{-11}	7.71×10^{-1}
1.00×10^{16}	1×10^{-1}	5×10^{-1}	5.81×10^{-10}	3.12×10^{-10}	1.08×10^0
1.00×10^{16}	1×10^{-1}	1.0	1.03×10^{-9}	3.13×10^{-10}	8.10×10^{-1}
1.00×10^{16}	5×10^{-1}	2.0	1.67×10^{-9}	4.19×10^{-10}	7.50×10^{-1}
1.00×10^{17}	1×10^{-1}	5×10^{-1}	5.97×10^{-9}	3.21×10^{-9}	1.05×10^0
1.00×10^{17}	1×10^{-1}	1.0	1.06×10^{-8}	3.22×10^{-9}	7.88×10^{-1}
1.00×10^{17}	5×10^{-1}	2.0	1.72×10^{-8}	4.30×10^{-9}	7.30×10^{-1}

($M_L \gtrsim 10^{15} \text{ kg}$) and for typical cosmological redshifts, the required spectral resolution is well within the capabilities of current high-resolution spectrographs (e.g., $R \sim 10^4\text{--}10^5$). Therefore, if a bright enough source exists and the lens is suitably aligned, the energy fringes could in principle be resolved.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Our analysis considered four distinct lensing scenarios that combine gravitational lensing with HR, as illustrated in Figs. 2–5:

1. **Standard lensing (no HR)**: Light from a background source is lensed by a black hole (BH) that

FIG. 11. Required spectral resolution $\Delta\lambda_{\min}$ vs. lens mass for a fixed source redshift $z_S = 1$ and lens redshift $z_L = 0.1$. The blue solid curve corresponds to HR from the source, the red dashed curve to HR from the lens. Horizontal lines mark the spectral resolution of instruments with resolving power $R = 1000$, 10^4 , and 10^5 at a reference wavelength of 1 \AA . (See section V F.))

does not emit HR. This is the classical geometric optics case where only the lensing deflection affects the light path.

2. **Lensing with HR from the lens:** The lens is a BH that emits HR. The background light is lensed and also interacts with the HR photons from the lens, potentially leading to spectral distortions.
3. **Both source and lens emit HR:** The source is a BH emitting HR, and the lens is also a BH emitting HR. The lensed HR from the source is superposed with the HR from the lens, and both are affected by the gravitational field of the lens.
4. **Source emits HR, lens does not:** A BH source emits HR, which is then lensed by a BH lens that does not emit HR. This is the case where the lens acts purely as a gravitational deflector for the HR from the source.

Our analysis concentrates on the physical implications of the 4th HR femtolensing configuration (Figure 5), where a non-emitting BH acts as a lens for a background source that emits Hawking radiation. This case offers the cleanest theoretical signature for detecting PBH evaporation. Without gravitational lensing, the intrinsic Hawking radiation flux from a PBH at astrophysical distances would be far below any realistic detection threshold.

Lensing is therefore not merely an enhancement but an essential requirement for any possible detection of this signal. The other three scenarios, although interesting, are left for subsequent investigations.

Inspired by these scenarios, we evaluated the relevant coherence conditions (spatial, temporal, and spectral) and the photon flux to determine whether the HR signatures could be detected. The mathematical framework (Sect. IV) provided the necessary relations for the Schwarzschild radius, Einstein radius, Hawking temperature, peak wavelength, and path difference. Cosmological distances were computed in a flat Λ CDM universe ($\Omega_{m0} = 0.3$, $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$) to correctly account for redshift effects on distances, fluxes, and angular sizes. Therefore, our analysis for the first time connects the idea of femtolensing HR to the evolution of the universe, the Hubble expansion rate today, dark energy, and other types of energy densities of the universe. This can lead to a novel observational signature of dark energy, and the evolution of the universe, through HR, and PBH. Potentially these studies could change our understanding about cosmology.

The analysis revealed that, the spectral coherence condition is easily met for PBH masses of interest ($M_L \gtrsim 10^{15} \text{ kg}$). The most promising avenue to observe femtolensing effects is to use a bright, narrow-line background source (e.g., an AGN X-ray line) as the lensed

FIG. 12. Required spectral resolution $\Delta\lambda_{\min}$ vs. source redshift for a fixed lens mass $M_L = 10^{16}$ kg and lens redshift $z_L = 10^{-3}$. Blue solid: HR from source; red dashed: HR from lens. The coloured dashed curves show the resolution achievable with $R = 1000, 10^4, 10^5$ for the source-emitted case; the horizontal dotted lines show the same for the lens-emitted case. (See section V F.)

object; in that case, the energy fringes from the lensing of the background source can be detectable with current instruments.

We have performed a systematic study of the detectability of HR from PBHs, considering both direct detection and the possibility of femtolensing enhancement. Our analysis combined cosmological distance calculations, HR properties. The main results are as follows:

In this work, we have developed a comprehensive framework for the femtolensing of Hawking radiation (HR) from primordial black holes (PBHs). Our analysis focused on the most promising scenario: a non-emitting black hole acting as a lens for a background PBH source that emits HR (Case 4 in Figure 5). We evaluated the maximum magnified photon flux $\Phi_{\text{HR, lensed}}$ using wave-optics magnification in the perfect alignment limit ($\beta = 0$).

our key findings are

- **General trends:** The maximum magnified HR photon flux increases when:
 - the lens redshift z_L increases,
 - the source redshift z_S decreases,
 - the lens mass M_L increases,
 - the source mass M_S decreases,
 - the Hubble constant H_0 increases,

– the matter density Ω_{m0} increases (equivalently, dark energy density Ω_Λ decreases).

- **Late-universe contours:** At redshifts $z_L = 1$, $z_S = 2$, detectable signals require a high lens-to-source mass ratio. For source masses $M_S \in [10^6, 10^8]$ kg and lens masses $M_L \in [10^{36}, 10^{40}]$ kg, the flux exceeds the observational threshold ($\Phi_{\min} = 62 \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$). This suggests that if PBHs in the asteroid-mass range exist, they could be detected via femtolensing by supermassive black holes.
- **Cosmological dependence:** The flux increases monotonically with both H_0 and Ω_{m0} (for fixed masses and redshifts). This arises from the luminosity distance scaling: larger H_0 or larger Ω_{m0} reduces the comoving distance, boosting the intrinsic HR flux. Thus, a detection (or non-detection) of femtolensed HR could, in principle, constrain cosmological parameters, complementing traditional probes like the CMB and supernovae.
- **Local universe applications:** For a lens at $z_L = 10^{-6}$, the most favourable configuration combines a supermassive lens ($M_L = 10^{40}$ kg) with a very light source ($M_S = 10^6$ kg), yielding detectable signals up to $z_S \sim 100$. Heavier sources ($M_S \geq 10^{10}$ kg) drastically reduce the redshift reach, and for $M_S =$

10^{15} kg no detectable signal is possible even with the heaviest lenses.

The implications of our results demonstrate that the femtolensing of Hawking radiation is most sensitive to extremely light PBHs (asteroid-mass or smaller) acting as sources, lensed by supermassive black holes. The strong dependence on the mass ratio M_L/M_S and on cosmological parameters offers a new avenue to probe both PBH dark matter and the expansion history of the universe. Future surveys targeting high-redshift sources with massive foreground lenses could potentially discover such events. The remaining three femtolensing scenarios (Cases 1–3) are deferred to a future study.

This framework bridges quantum gravity (Hawking radiation) with gravitational lensing and observational cosmology, establishing a unique probe of primordial black holes and the nature of dark matter and dark energy.

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CODE AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Code/software supporting our findings will become available upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

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Appendix A: Femtolensing formalism

Following [20, 21, 23], we consider a point mass lens of mass M at angular diameter distance $D_L = D_{OL}$ from the observer, and a source at distance $D_{OS} = D_S$. The angular diameter distance from the lens to the source is D_{LS} .

Note that from Hartle [22] geometric and schematic approach, and in the thin-angle approximation, the *lens equation* is given by:

$$\theta D_S = \beta D_S + \alpha D_{LS} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Given that

$$\alpha(\theta) = \frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{1}{\theta D_L} = 2R_s \frac{1}{\theta D_L} \quad (\text{A2})$$

one can derive the equation:

$$\theta = \beta + \frac{\theta_E^2}{\theta} \quad (\text{A3})$$

the Einstein angle (or Einstein angular radius):

$$\theta_E = \sqrt{\frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} = \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

the corresponding physical Einstein radius is

$$R_E = \theta_E D_L. \quad (\text{A5})$$

Therefore we get that the Einstein radius for a lens of mass M , with Schwarzschild radius, R_s is given by:

$$R_E = \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS} D_L}{D_S}} = \sqrt{\frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS} D_L}{D_S}}. \quad (\text{A6})$$

Combined we have relation between Einstein radius, Einstein angular radius, Schwarzschild radius, comoving distance of the observer to lens, comoving distance between source and observer, and comoving distance between lens and source:

$$\theta_E = \frac{R_E}{D_L} = \sqrt{\frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} = \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

Appendix B: Time delay in gravitational lensed system

In the thin-lens approximation, the total time delay for a light ray forming an image at angular position θ (relative to the undeflected ray) is the sum of a geometric delay and a gravitational delay [20, 21]:

$$\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{1}{c} \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} |\theta - \beta|^2 - \psi(\theta) \right], \quad (\text{B1})$$

where β is the angular position of the source, and ψ is the lensing potential. The *lens equation* relates source and image positions:

$$\beta = \theta - \alpha(\theta) \Leftrightarrow \alpha(\theta) = \theta - \beta \Leftrightarrow \theta = \alpha(\theta) - \beta \quad (\text{B2})$$

Then, we get that the time delay is

$$\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{1}{c} \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} |\alpha(\theta)|^2 - \psi(\theta) \right]. \quad (\text{B3})$$

For a point mass, the lensing potential was derived in Appendix A from [23]. According to [23] the β is the angle under which the observer would see the source in the absence of a lens, and θ is the angle under which the observer sees a given point in the lens plane, and the function $\psi(\theta)$ is the lensing potential. The lensing potential is described as

$$\psi(\theta) = \frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta|. \quad (\text{B4})$$

The lensing potential can be expressed in terms of R_s can be also written simply as

$$\psi(\theta) = 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta|, \quad (\text{B5})$$

or simply:

$$\psi(\theta) = 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta|. \quad (\text{B6})$$

Following from equation 92 from [21], the deflection angle α is given by the gradient of the potential:

$$\alpha(\theta) = \nabla_{\theta} \psi(\theta) \quad (\text{B7})$$

Substituting and expanding we get

$$\alpha(\theta) = \frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{\theta}{|\theta|^2}. \quad (\text{B8})$$

which in 1 dimension of θ , and 1 dimension in deflection angle, α , this is written simply as

$$\alpha(\theta) = \frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta} = 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta}. \quad (\text{B9})$$

Appendix C: Deriving the path difference in a gravitationally lensed object

Following definitions and equations from [20–23], We assume that the path difference is approximately

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} |\alpha(\theta)|^2 - \psi(\theta) \right]. \quad (\text{C1})$$

or simply

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} |\alpha(\theta)|^2 - \psi(\theta) \right]. \quad (\text{C2})$$

now substituting the angle of deflection:

$$\alpha(\theta) = \frac{4GM}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta} = 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta}. \quad (\text{C3})$$

we get

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta} \right)^2 - \psi(\theta) \right] \quad (\text{C4})$$

now we substitute the lensing potential formula,

$$\psi(\theta) = 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta|. \quad (\text{C5})$$

and we get:

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \frac{1}{\theta} \right)^2 - 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta| \right] \quad (\text{C6})$$

factorising:

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{1}{\theta} \right)^2 - 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \ln |\theta| \right] \quad (\text{C7})$$

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = \frac{D_L D_S}{D_{LS}} (1 + z_L) 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \left[\frac{1}{2} 2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \times \left(\frac{1}{\theta} \right)^2 - \ln |\theta| \right] \quad (\text{C8})$$

$$\Delta l(\theta) \approx c\Delta t(\theta) = (1 + z_L) 2R_s \left[R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \times \frac{1}{\theta^2} - \ln |\theta| \right] \quad (\text{C9})$$

now substituting $\theta \rightarrow \theta_E$, we get

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L) 2R_s \left[R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \times \frac{1}{\theta_E^2} - \ln |\theta_E| \right] \quad (\text{C10})$$

but the Einstein angle is :

$$\theta_E = \frac{R_E}{D_L} = \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \quad (\text{C11})$$

so we substitute the Einstein angle to get:

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L) 2R_s \left[R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S} \times \frac{D_L D_S}{2R_s D_{LS}} - \ln \left| \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \right| \right] \quad (\text{C12})$$

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L) 2R_s \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln \left| \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \right| \right] \quad (\text{C13})$$

So we can write this result simply as

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L)2R_s \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln|\theta_E| \right] \quad (\text{C14})$$

or

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L)2R_s \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right] \quad (\text{C15})$$

or

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L) \left[R_s - 2R_s \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right] \quad (\text{C16})$$

or

$$\Delta l(\theta_E) \approx c\Delta t(\theta_E) = (1 + z_L) \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{R_E^2}{D_L} - 2R_s \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right] \quad (\text{C17})$$

or for our local group, we had that

$$z_L \approx 0 \rightarrow 1 + z_L \approx 1 \quad (\text{C18})$$

so we get

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{R_E^2}{D_L} - 2R_s \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right], \quad (\text{C19})$$

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \left[R_s - 2R_s \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right], \quad (\text{C20})$$

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 2R_s \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right| \right], \quad (\text{C21})$$

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 2R_s \left[\ln e^{\frac{1}{2}} + \ln\left|\frac{R_E}{D_L}\right|^{-1} \right], \quad (\text{C22})$$

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 2R_s \left[\ln e^{\frac{1}{2}} \left|\frac{D_L}{R_E}\right| \right], \quad (\text{C23})$$

$$(\text{C24})$$

and if we evaluate we get

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 2R_s \left[\ln\left(e^{\frac{1}{2}} \left|\frac{D_L}{R_E}\right| \right) \right], \quad (\text{C25})$$

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 2 \times 2.95 \times 10^{-10} \left[\ln\left(e^{\frac{1}{2}} \left|\frac{3.086 \times 10^{21}}{1.35 \times 10^6}\right| \right) \right], \quad (\text{C26})$$

which means we get

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \approx 2 \times 2.95 \times 10^{-10} \times 35 \quad (\text{C27})$$

or in other words this is

$$\Delta l \approx c\Delta t(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \approx 70R_s. \quad (\text{C28})$$

Following [20–23], using a geometric and gravitational approach, and in the thin-angle approximation, we consider a point mass lens of mass M_L , at some lens redshift, z_L , at angular diameter distance D_L from the observer, and a source at distance D_S , and the angular diameter distance from the lens to the source is D_{LS} . In a general case, the path difference is related to the mass, and the distances, as :

$$\Delta l(M_L, D_L, D_S, D_{LS}) \approx c\Delta t = (1 + z_L) \frac{4GM_L}{c^2} \left[\frac{1}{2} - \ln\left| \sqrt{\frac{4GM_L}{c^2} \frac{D_{LS}}{D_L D_S}} \right| \right]. \quad (\text{C29})$$

Appendix D: Basic numerical evaluation

Constants:

1. Common Parameters and Derived Scales

Given the following numerical values we calculate the necessary quantities.

- $G = 6.674 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$
- $c = 3.0 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$
- $\hbar = 1.055 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J s}$
- $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J s}$
- $k_B = 1.381 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$
- $M_\odot = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$

Cosmology framework:

- Flat homogeneous, isotropic, expanding universe, field with matter.
- $\Omega_{m0} = 3.000 \times 10^{-1}$
- $H_0 = 7.000 \times 10^4 \text{ m/s/Mpc}$
- $z_L = 1.000 \times 10^{-5}$
- $D_{\text{comoving}} = 4.286 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Mpc}$

System parameters:

- $M = 1.000 \times 10^{-16} M_\odot = 1.989 \times 10^{14} \text{ kg}$
- $z_L = 1.000 \times 10^{-5}$
- $D_L(z_L) = 1.323 \times 10^9 \text{ m} = 4.286 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Mpc}$
- $\Delta z_{LS} = 1.000 \times 10^{-3}$
- $z_S = 1.010 \times 10^{-3}$
- $D_S(z_S) = 1.337 \times 10^{11} \text{ m} = 4.334 \times 10^0 \text{ Mpc}$
- $D_{LS} = 1.324 \times 10^{11} \text{ m} = 4.291 \times 10^0 \text{ Mpc}$
- $v_\perp = 2.000 \times 10^5 \text{ m/s}$ (typical galactic transverse velocity)

2. Lensing Scales

- **Schwarzschild radius:**

$$R_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2} \quad (\text{D1})$$

$$R_s = 1.4852 \times 10^{-27} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}, \quad (\text{D2})$$

$$R_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2} = 2.950 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m} \approx 10^{-13} \text{ m}$$

- **Einstein radius:** $R_E \approx \sqrt{2R_s \frac{D_{LS} D_L}{D_S}} = 2.780 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m} \approx 10^{-2} \text{ m}$
- **Lensing angle:** $\theta_E = \frac{R_E}{D_L} = 2.1016 \times 10^{-11} \text{ rad} \approx 4334850345.48 \text{ femtoarcsec}$
- **Lensing timescale:** $t_E = \frac{R_E}{v_\perp} = 1.390 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s} \approx 1.61 \times 10^{-12} \text{ days}$
- **Path difference:** $\Delta l = \Delta l(M, D_L, D_S, D_{LS}) = 7.400 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m} \approx 10^{-12} \text{ m}$
- **Lensing time delay:** $\Delta t = \frac{\Delta l}{c} = 2.467 \times 10^{-20} \text{ s} \approx 2.85 \times 10^{-25} \text{ days}$

3. Hawking Radiation Properties

- **Hawking temperature:** $T_{\text{HR}} = \frac{\hbar c^3}{8\pi G M k_B} = 6.182 \times 10^8 \text{ K} \approx 10^8$
- **HR energy:** $E = 2.8 k_B T_H = 1.492 \times 10^5 \text{ eV} \approx 10^5 \text{ eV}$
- **HR wavelength:**

$$\lambda_{\text{HR}} \approx \frac{hc}{2.8 k_B T_H}, \quad (\text{D3})$$

$$\lambda_{\text{HR}} \approx \frac{16\pi^2 G_N}{2.8 c^2} M, \quad (\text{D4})$$

$$\lambda_{\text{HR}} \approx 4.18 \times 10^{-26} \left(\frac{M}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}, \quad (\text{D5})$$

$$\lambda_{\text{HR}} \approx 8.315 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m} \approx 10^{-12} \text{ m}. \quad (\text{D6})$$

4. Lifetime Constraint

The evaporation lifetime of a PBH is

$$t_{\text{ev}} = \frac{5120\pi G^2}{\hbar c^4} M^3. \quad (\text{D7})$$

Setting $t_{\text{ev}} = t_U$ (age of the universe $\approx 1.38 \times 10^{10} \text{ yr}$) gives a minimum mass for survival:

$$M_{\text{min}} = \left(\frac{\hbar c^4 t_U}{5120\pi G^2} \right)^{1/3} \approx 1.732 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg} \approx 8.707 \times 10^{-20} M_\odot. \quad (\text{D8})$$

PBHs with $M < M_{\text{min}}$ would have already evaporated unless formed very recently.

5. Interference

- **Path difference:** $\Delta l = \Delta l(M, D_L, D_S, D_{LS}) = 7.400 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m} \approx 10^{-12} \text{ m}$

These results, provides the orders of magnitudes for the femtolensing Hawking radiation signature.

Appendix E: Magnification details

Following the formalism in [33], and keep the notation of recent studies [23], and considering the dimensionless angular frequency parameter ϖ , we introduce the dimensionless variable β modelled as :

$$\beta = \frac{\theta_\perp}{\theta_E}, \quad (\text{E1})$$

while the amplification factor, is denoted with $F(\varpi, \beta)$. Then the magnification is written as

$$\mu(\varpi, \beta) = |F(\varpi, \beta)|^2. \quad (\text{E2})$$

The maximum magnification is achieved in maximum alignment, i.e. when

$$\theta_+ = 0 \Leftrightarrow \beta = 0. \quad (\text{E3})$$

In maximum alignment, the maximum magnification is

$$\mu_{\max}(\varpi) = \mu(\varpi, \beta = 0) \quad (\text{E4})$$

which yields:

$$\mu_{\max}(\varpi) = \frac{\pi\varpi}{1 - e^{-\pi\varpi}}. \quad (\text{E5})$$

The expression for the dimensionless angular frequency parameter ϖ (including redshift) is:

$$\varpi = \frac{1}{c} \frac{D_S D_L}{D_{LS}} \theta_E^2 (1 + z_L) \omega^{(\text{source})} \quad (\text{E6})$$

where $\omega^{(\text{source})} = \frac{2\pi c}{\lambda^{(\text{source})}}$ is the angular frequency of the source emitter.

We can rewrite the previous expression as :

$$\varpi = (1 + z_L) \frac{4\pi R_s^{(\text{lens})}(M_L)}{\lambda^{(\text{source})}(M_S)} \quad (\text{E7})$$

Now we consider the case in which the source, and then lens are both BH, and the source emits at the HR wavelength, then we get

$$\varpi = 4\pi (1 + z_L) \frac{R_s^{(\text{lens})}}{\lambda_{\text{HR}}^{(\text{source})}}. \quad (\text{E8})$$

Since the BHs are not the same, we assume a priori :

$$M_{(\text{lens})} \neq M_{(\text{source})} \quad (\text{E9})$$

Substituting the proportional relations:

$$R_s^{(\text{lens})} = \frac{2G_N M_L}{c^2} \approx 1.4852 \times 10^{-27} \left(\frac{M_L}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}, \quad (\text{E10})$$

$$\lambda_{\text{HR}}^{(\text{source})} \approx \frac{16\pi^2 G_N}{2.8 c^2} M_s \approx 4.18 \times 10^{-26} \left(\frac{M_S}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}, \quad (\text{E11})$$

yielding:

$$\varpi = 4\pi (1 + z_L) \frac{R_s^{(\text{lens})}}{\lambda_{\text{HR}}^{(\text{source})}} \quad (\text{E12})$$

$$\varpi = (1 + z_L) \frac{2.8 M_L}{2\pi M_S} \quad (\text{E13})$$

$$\varpi = 4\pi (1 + z_L) \frac{1.4852 \times 10^{-27} \left(\frac{M_L}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}}{4.18 \times 10^{-26} \left(\frac{M_S}{\text{kg}} \right) \text{ m}} \quad (\text{E14})$$

$$\varpi = 0.44563384065 (1 + z_L) \frac{\left(\frac{M_L}{\text{kg}} \right)}{\left(\frac{M_S}{\text{kg}} \right)} \quad (\text{E15})$$

$$\varpi \approx \frac{2.8}{2\pi} (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right) \quad (\text{E16})$$

Hence, in maximum alignment, the maximum magnification has multiple dependences, i.e. the maximum magnification depends on the mass of the lens, M_L , of the source, M_S , and the redshift of the lens, z_L , and we write

$$\mu_{\max}(z_L, M_L, M_S) = \frac{1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}{1 - e^{-1.4 (1 + z_L) \left(\frac{M_L}{M_S} \right)}}. \quad (\text{E17})$$

1. Comparison of Magnification Formulas

The three expressions for magnification presented in different studies [23, 33] describe different regimes and levels of approximation. Understanding their relationship is essential for correctly interpreting femtolensing observations.

- **General wave-optics magnification:** $\mu(\varpi, \beta) = |F(\varpi, \beta)|^2$ is the most complete description. It accounts for diffraction and interference, and applies for all values of the dimensionless frequency parameter $\varpi = 4\pi(1 + z_L)R_s^{(\text{lens})}/\lambda^{(\text{source})}$ and angular offset β . In the short-wavelength limit ($\varpi \rightarrow \infty$), it reproduces geometric optics, while for $\varpi \sim 1$ it captures the interference fringes that define the femtolensing regime.
- **Maximum magnification (perfect alignment, $\beta = 0$):** $\mu_{\max}(\varpi) = \frac{\pi\varpi}{1 - e^{-\pi\varpi}}$ is a special case of the wave-optics formula. It gives the finite peak value at $\beta = 0$, which remains finite due to wave effects. In the geometric limit ($\varpi \gg 1$), it approximates $\mu_{\max} \approx \pi\varpi$, which matches the familiar divergence $2/\beta$ only if one artificially sets $\beta = 2/(\pi\varpi)$.
- **Geometric optics approximation:** $\mu_{\text{geo}}(\beta) = \frac{\beta^2 + 2}{\beta\sqrt{\beta^2 + 4}}$ is valid only when $\varpi \gg 1$ (short wavelengths) and for $\beta > 0$. It diverges as $\beta \rightarrow 0$, which is unphysical when wave effects are important. Therefore, it should not be used for fem-

tolensing of Hawking radiation, where $\varpi \sim 1$. Instead, the wave-optics formula must be employed, especially near perfect alignment.

In this work, we adopt the wave-optics formalism

throughout, and we use the maximum magnification ($\beta = 0$) to estimate the best-case scenario for detection. The geometric optics formula is shown only for comparison and is not used in our numerical estimates because it would severely overestimate the magnification for our parameters.